

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1B

Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy,
Astropy)

Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)

General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)

yt

-

xarray

Chris Havlin

Matt Turk

Facilitating Software Reuse Between Space and Earth Sciences

Full Presentation

<https://bit.ly/ytxrpdf> <https://bit.ly/ytxrweb>

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School of Information Sciences

Embedded transformations for volume rendering without pre-interpolation!

Relative humidity in subset of MERRA-2 data product (with vertical exaggeration):

Leveraging cloud-ready data formats!

(1) Zarr / remote data access via xarray backend:

(2) investigating Zarr for AMR, Octree, SPH

Full Presentation:

<https://bit.ly/ytxrpdf> <https://bit.ly/ytxrweb>

PlanetaryPy: a Python community for Planetary Science

Dr. Andrew M. Annex*, Michael Aye, Ross Beyer,
Chase Million, Christian J. Tai Udovicic
<https://planetarypy.org/>

PlanetaryPy is a community lead effort established initially in 2015 to foster and grow a community of Python software practitioners within the Planetary Science Division (PSD). The PlanetaryPy Technical Committee (TC) is the governing body for the PlanetaryPy, which conducts meetings open to the public with minutes preserved at the TC GitHub repository. The goals of PlanetaryPy are to develop a core Python package for planetary science and to encourage and communicate open-source best practices to the broader community to help ensure compatibility between software packages. Topics of best practices maintained by PlanetaryPy include governance topics like code-of-conducts and software licenses, and software maintainability standards such as emphasizing test coverage and minimum supported Python versions. In addition to reviewing repositories for inclusion as affiliated packages that meet these standards, PlanetaryPy is investigating the addition of an incubation stage for projects that are still in early development.

PlanetaryPy aims to increase use of Python and open source best practices in PSD

1. Monthly meetings open to the public advertised at <https://github.com/planetarypy/TC>
Please join! All are welcome!
 - a. We aim to advise projects at all stages of development.
 - b. We aim to make goals of TOPS/SPD41a easier for scientists/engineers to achieve in PSD.
2. Open Governance Documents, Code of Conduct, Charter, Coding Standards all available for adoption for easier onramp to best practices (SPD41a, TOPS)
3. Different stages of affiliations and requirements (Affiliated, Incubating (soon), Scriptorium)
4. PlanetaryPy core library aimed for initial release soon (summer 2024)

SpiceyPy: an open source exemplar in PSD

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*(image(s) credit AMNH, NYC)

SpiceyPy is an cross-platform, open source, community produced Python library wrapper for NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory's (JPL) Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility (NAIF) SPICE (Spacecraft, Planet, Instrument, C-matrix, Events) toolkit. SpiceyPy is used widely within the Planetary Science and Heliophysics divisions of SMD for scientific research and mission operations in all phases of mission development and across all mission classes. Examples of missions using SpiceyPy in science and or engineering include M2020, Parker Solar Probe, Europa Clipper, MRO, and DART. SpiceyPy began development in 2014 with the first major public version release in 2016 helping to establish open source best practices that other planetary science software libraries now follow. The library is developed on GitHub and uses continuous integration (CI) services to publish binary artifacts, run the extensive test suite, and to generate the web accessible documentation on the ReadTheDocs service. SpiceyPy is an affiliated package of PlanetaryPy which helps foster open source development in planetary science.

SpiceyPy: The Python interface to SPICE

Who:

**Dr. Andrew Annex &
community contributors**

What:

**MIT Python wrapper for
SPICE Toolkit from NASA
JPL**

When:

In development since 2014

Where:

**PyPI & Conda Forge &
GitHub**

github.com/andrewannex/spiceypy

*(image(s) credit AMNH, NYC)

The Planetary Data Reader (pdr) is an open-source Python tool intended to read all PDS-compliant data products with one command: `pdr.read()`

- Development is ongoing, and the first stable version was released last year
- A simple and robust interface
- Highly optimized
 - 14 Mastcam-Z images in ~250 ms
 - Metadata from 1000 Diviner products in ~1.5 s
- Designed for maximum compatibility with the standard scientific Python stack
- *pdr* has already served as an essential component of multiple production applications
 - Tactical-timeline multispectral analyses for M2020 Mastcam-Z
 - PDS3 → PDS4 conversion pipelines for M3, Clementine, and Viking data sets

Regression-tested ("official") support for >50% of PDS products, including data sets from:

Voyager	Galileo	Juno	New Horizons
Magellan	Giotto	Dawn	MESSENGER
Cassini	Apollo	LRO	Chandrayaan-1
MER	MRO	MSL	and more...

With probable support for >90% of products.

To request priority support for datasets of interest, see instructions at github.com/MillionConcepts/pdr

```
>>> import pdr
>>> data = pdr.read("ch1/M3_L2/M3T20090418T074719_V01_L2.LBL")
>>> print(type(data.RFL_IMAGE))
>>> data.show("RFL_IMAGE")
```

`<class 'numpy.ndarray'>`

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Building Open Science Skills and Cultural Competency in the Community: Knowing the Sky

Knowing the Sky: an Overview

- Interactive, self-paced course in open science data tools and techniques
- Centers on skills, data, and workflows relevant to planetary science and astronomy
- Target audience: Laypeople to experienced scientists
- Next step for space science python users (with a path for transitioning users)
- Narrative-driven with Native knowledge concepts

Artwork by Shandin Pete (2021)

Part	Name	Skills
1	Gathering the Sky	Getting data from NASA cloud sources. Managing data locally.
2	Ordering the Sky	Opening tables and arrays. Indexing and array visualization.
3	Drawing the Sky	Creating plots. Working with time and coordinates.
4	Naming the Sky	Parsing text with regular expressions. Producing descriptive statistics. Model fitting.
5	Measuring the Sky	Working with SPICE. Building symbolic expressions.
6	Seeing the Moon	Image processing: filtering and masking images. Similarity analysis using computer vision.
7	Describing the Moon	Preprocessing data for AI/ML pipelines. Using classification and decomposition models.
8	Sharing the Moon	Creating and versioning GitHub repositories. Managing data on AWS S3.
9-10	TBD	TBD (based on community input)